

PROPER PLANTING DATES FOR NEWLY CREATED "NIYAT" CULTIVAR OF HOT PEPPER (CAPSICUM ANNUUM L.) IN UNHEATED GREENHOUSES IN THE CONDITIONS OF TASHKENT REGION TO OBTAIN A HIGH YIELD AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY

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Melon crops and Potato growing

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Abstract. The article presents the data on the yield performance of new cultivars of hot pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) (chili pepper) suitable for p

Key words. New cultivar, greenhouse, fruit, hot pepper, harvest, yield, planting dates, plant.

Introduction. In recent years, in the world, scientific researches are being carried out to create new cultivars of the hot pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) suitable for growing in unheated greenhouses, with a level of bitterness above 10 points, exportable, with good fruit quality, with a yield of 80-90 t/ha and also to determine their optimal planting dates and schemes using innovative methods. Hot pepper is the main crop in the leading countries in the cultivation of hot pepper, and it is also widely used in the industrial and pharmaceutical fields. Therefore, creating high-yielding varieties of hot pepper suitable for cultivation in unheated greenhouse conditions is an important scientific direction. Selection of its varieties suitable for growing in unheated greenhouse conditions and development of important elements of cultivation technology, as well as providing the population with fresh and new products throughout the year, is one of the urgent tasks of today.

The purpose of the study is to create hot pepper (*Capsicum annuum* L.) cultivars with high yield and good fruit quality suitable for growing in greenhouses.

The methods of the study. The research in the greenhouse and laboratory was conducting according to "Methodology of experimental work in vegetable and melon growing", "Methodology of conducting experiments in vegetable, melon crops and potato growing", "Guidelines for the study and keeping the world collection of vegetable nightshade crops (tomatoes, peppers, eggplants)", "Guidelines for conducting experiments with vegetable crops in protected ground structures (SRIVF)", and the statistical analysis of the results

was carried out using the Microsoft Excel program and the dispersion analysis method of B.A. Dospekhov.

The results of the study and their discussion. It is known that the planting dates has high influence on the productivity of vegetable crops, therefore it is necessary to know how to correctly choose the planting time in order to obtain high yield and good-quality harvest. During the ripening period of the fruits, in the control option of the experiment the cultivar "Sharq gavhari" produced the fruits per plant 125 pieces, when it was planted in the first option, the number of the plant fruits was 112 pieces, or 10.4% less than the control, and when planted in the second and fourth options, there was no significant difference from the control, that is, 116–128 fruits or 0.2–7.2% more than the control. The weight of fruit of hot pepper was 19 g in the control variant, 14.3–15.4 g in the first and second variants, or 18.9–24.7% lighter than the control. Total fruit weight was 2.3 kg in the control option, it was 1.6 kg or 30.4% in plants planted in the first option compared to the control, when planted in the second variant the indicator was 1.7 kg or 26.1% lighter than the control. In the fourth option it was found to be 2.6 kg or 13% heavier than the control.

Marketable fruit weight and number of fruits per bush of hot pepper cultivars planted in different planting dates under unheated greenhouse conditions

(in 2020–2023)

Planting dates	During ripening period per bush								
	Fruit number		Weight of one fruit		Weight of total fruit		Yield		
	piece	%	g	%	kg	%	kg/m ²	%	
"Sharq gavhari" cultivar									
February 10	112,0	89,6	14,3	75,3	1,6	69,6	5,6	70	
February 20	116,0	92,8	15,4	81,1	1,7	73,9	5,9	73,8	
March 1 (control)	125,0	100,0	19,0	100,0	2,3	100,0	8,0	100	
March 10	128,0	102,4	20,3	106,8	2,6	113,0	9,1	113,8	
×	120,3	96,2	16,9	88,3	2,0	85,9	7,2	89,4	
L							2,2		
Sx,%							2,7		
	r=0,99±0,11								
"Niyat" cultivar									
February 10	91,0	93,8	17,2	84,3	1,5	78,9	5,2	78,8	

February 20	93,0	95,9	18,3	89,7	1,7	89,5	5,9	89,4
March 1 (control)	97,0	100	20,4	100,0	1,9	100,0	6,6	100,0
March 10	107,0	110,3	21,2	103,9	2,2	115,8	7,7	116,7
×	97,0	100	19,3	94,5	1,8	96,1	6,4	96,2
L							2,7	
Sx,%							3,1	
	r=0,92±0,12							

Y

i In the "Niyat" cultivar, the number of fruits per plant was 97.0 pieces in the control option, while in the first and second options it was 91-93 pieces, or 4.1-6.2% less than the control. Plants of this cultivar planted in the fourth option had 107.0 fruits or 10.3% more than the control. The weight of one fruit was 20.4 g in the control option, 17.2–18.3 g in the first and second options, or 10.3–15.7% less than the control, and 21.2 pieces in the option with a 10-day delay in planting, or more than the control, that is, increased by 3.9 percent.

r The total weight of fruits per bush was 1.9 kg in the control option, while it was 1.5–1.7 kg in plants in the first and second option, or 10.5–20.1% less than the control. In plants planted in the fourth option, the indicator was 2.2 kg or 15.8% more than the control. The same result was observed in the number of fruits, weight of one fruit, weight of total fruits and productivity per square meter in the cultivar "Tillarang". The correlation between the number of fruits per plant and the weight of the total fruits during the period of maturity of the fruits was strong, $r=0.99\pm 0.11$ in the cultivar "Sharq gavhari".

Conclusion. When we planted the newly created hot pepper varieties "Sharq gavhari" and "Niyat" suitable for growing in unheated greenhouses in the conditions of Tashkent region in 2020-2023 from February 10 to March 10, we found that the yield per square meter was higher when planted in March 1-10.

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